

Football Players Market Value Prediction Using Machine Learning

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Abstract — Soccer clubs spend enormous amount of money to buy professional soccer players each year during the transfer window. Predicting the value of a player in the transfer market is one of the difficult tasks for a club manager. Transfermarkt.com uses football professionals to determine the value of a player. Due to the need for crowdsourcing, is rarely updated with many users participating, are error prone, and data scientists use this topic to use data from around the world. And create a dataset and an estimation method. The data-driven method seems to be an alternative approach for crowd-driven website to estimate the market value of player. Regression analysis was used to estimate the market value of players. Player stats like height, weight, player position, speed, physis, overall, potential, defending, dribbling, passing and mentality is selected as the training dataset.

Keywords—soccer, transfer, data-driven, regression

I. INTRODUCTION

Soccer is one of the most popular sports worldwide. Many countries have players who compete in regional and national tournaments. The English Premier League is the most popular sport in the world, with 6434.44 million households in 212 countries watching it. Researchers have just started to consider the market value of players. Looking broadly to the future of soccer games, system modelling is very much important in terms of economic value, but its not just academic interest. The market value of players have received a lot of attention from researchers. Players can sell their contract from one team to another and then estimate their market values. Although referral fee is expressed at the price actually paid. The referral transaction plays an important role in the market value offered to as a referral fee. The market estimation from information driven method is not widespread in the world of expert football. Due to many uncertainties such as short career spans, risk of injury, club budgets, and different forms of the entire career, both clubs and players are continually trying to maximize performance. In addition to the charm of the game, there are other themes that are appealing to fans. One of them is the transfer of players during the transfer window. Fans wants to know which player would their favourite club will sign and how much club will spend during the transfer period. Predicting the market values on the basis of player stats would help club managers and even fans to arrive at an approximate market value of a player. The major contribution of this paper involves:

- Predicting the market values of football players on the basis of their stats
- Analysis to show players from which nationality are highly paid

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

B.Frick,[1] had done the paper, The football players' labor market: empirical evidence from the major European Leagues Scottish Journal of Political Economy (2007) which outlines the growing economic importance of professional soccer, as well as recent fundamental changes in the regulatory regime governing the labour market for soccer players. His study examines the evidence on various aspects of the football market that includes remuneration, transfers, contracts, and mobility

He,Cachucho & Knobbe,2015 [2] .Through their paper 'Football player's performance and market value,' specifies about football player's performance and market value procedures. They argue that elite player transfers in the main European football leagues are expensive, and that having a consistent economic value for football players throughout the year, rather than simply when a player has just transferred, is advantageous for a variety of reasons. They also emphasise the need of examining how a player's market value relates to his or her performance.

S.Herm, H,-M. Callsen-Bracker, H. Kries [3] 'Sport Management Review' is a survey that describes how an online community interested in professional soccer can assess a player's market value. It is also evident in their paper that community market value estimates are a good predictor of actual remittance fees.

Frank and Nuesch released a paper 'The Impact of Euro 2022 on Popularity and Market Value of Players' in 2012.This paper is based on player's popularity and wages. It forecasts the features that can improve a players performance and eventually his popularity that reflects their market values.

B. Torgler, S.L. Schmidt, Applied Economics,[5]. Individual data from eight seasons of the German soccer league Bundesliga is utilized in this study to investigate the pay-performance link of soccer players and find a nonlinear pay-performance relationship, suggesting that individual performance is influenced by compensation. The data also show that relative income position as well as absolute income level have an impact on player performance. A closer look at the impact of team effects on performance finds that

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teammate attributes have a direct impact on individual player performance.

III. MOTIVATION

Football is one of the most popular and widely watched sports on the planet. Football fans are eagerly waiting for each transfer window to witness which player will get transferred to which club and how much club would spend for the respective player. Players market value fluctuates according to their current player stats and traits. However, club management may wind up paying more for a player than they should. For the provided model, Regression Analysis visualization and various techniques are used. This methodology aids club managers in predicting player market value with utmost precision

IV. METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this project is to create a Machine Learning model that can accurately predict the market value of soccer players for the next transfer window based on the data provided that includes player stats and ability. The dataset contains a training and a testing data set. The model should be trained with more data to improve learning accuracy. The output of this model can be used to predict a player's market value. Linear Regression is used to forecast market prices

The structure is as follows:

Figure 1

The steps to be followed are:

1. Data Collection
2. Data Pre-processing
3. Model Building
4. Analyzing
5. Result

Data Collection: Data was gathered from the sofifa data pool for the training and testing datasets which contains stats of all

soccer players registered in fifa. From the year 2016, they feature both categorical and nominal statistics for player statistics and attributes. The dataset contains critical information regarding several significant features that may be used to estimate player's market value, such as skills, player traits, agility, strength, team position, potential, physic etc.

Data Cleaning: In the training dataset, the null values were deleted. Because they were unnecessary for the feature selection technique, a few columns in the dataset were eliminated. The columns of attributes with categorical data were removed from the dataset after the new columns with numerical values retrieved from the pre-processed data were stored for the prediction. As a result, we were able to create a suitable training dataset with the following attribute columns.

Formatting Data: Format the dataset, Drop unnecessary columns that do not have relevance in predicting the values, convert categorical values into numerical values for columns such as player traits, nationality, club , position etc.

Splitting Data: After the data has been formatted, it is divided into training and testing datasets .After that, we use the data we chose for training to train our model.

Machine Learning: This is intended to assist the user in accurately predicting the market value of a player. To estimate fares, machine learning algorithms will be applied with the dataset provided. To anticipate market value, various learning algorithms are applied. The training of machine learning algorithms is crucial. Which algorithm is optimal depends on the type of problem you're trying to solve, the computing resources you have, and the data you're working with. Here we use linear regression for predicting the values. Linear regression is a supervised learning machine learning algorithm. It carries out a regression task. Regression models a goal prediction value based on independent variables. It's generally used for forecasting and figuring out how variables are related. Different regression models have different types of relationships between dependent and independent variables. Gradient descent and cost function are the two most important factors in comprehending linear regression. The equation for linear regression is: $y(\text{pred}) = b_0 + b_1 * x$

The data is collected from sofifa.com that contains details and stats of players registered by fifa. The dataset contains 14882 rows and 104 columns. Each row represents a player from the year 2016. Editor used here is Google colab. The language used is python and the version of python is python 3.6. The modules used are pandas, numpy, matplotlib, plotly, sklearn and scipy. Pandas provides ready to use high-performance data structures and data analysis tools. Numpy is a general-purpose array-processing package. Matplotlib and plotly is used for plotting graph. Sklearn provides a selection of efficient tools for machine learning and statistical modeling including classification, regression, clustering and dimensionality reduction via a consistence interface in Python. The training dataset includes player stats like height, weight, player position, speed, physic, overall, potential,

defending, dribbling, passing and mentality. The test dataset is value of players.

V. IMPLEMENTATION

a. Initially, open your editor and create a new file, then import modules

```
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import plotly.graph_objects as go
import plotly.express as px
from sklearn.preprocessing import MinMaxScaler
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.linear_model import LinearRegression
from scipy.stats import ttest_ind
```

Figure 2: import module

players_16.head()

sofifa_id	player_url	short_name	long_name	age	dob	height_cm	weight_kg	nationality	club
158023	https://sofifa.com/player/158023/lionel-messi...	L. Messi	Lionel Andrés Messi Cucittini	28	1987-06-24	170	72	Argentina	FC Barcelona
20801	https://sofifa.com/player/20801/cristiano-ronaldo-dos...	Cristiano Ronaldo	Cristiano Ronaldo dos Santos Aveiro	30	1985-02-05	185	80	Portugal	Real Madrid

Figure3: Read dataset for model training

Figure4: Maximum player value per club

```
score=model.score(features_test,target_test)
score
0.6363645491778094
```

Figure5: Accuracy of Linear Regression

VI. RESULT

The experiment's outcome is described in this section. Using Linear Regression, we were able to determine the accuracy. The obtained accuracy is 0.63. The experiment's outcome

displays the anticipated player value matching to the player's fifa id.

sofifa_id	price
183745	4500000
216078	170000
193253	375000
212687	600000
163991	1300000
168393	30000
226537	1400000
183895	4100000
204348	400000
225335	425000

VII. CONCLUSION

This paper explains how to forecast soccer players market value. A set of data is collected, pre-processed, modelled, and investigated in order to test algorithmic rule. Machine Learning methods with square measure for predicting accurate player value. Data is obtained from websites that tracks and store data about soccer players. This could help club managers to have an approximate value of a certain player for the next transfer window.

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